

Perceived Influence of Digital Instructional Media Utilization on Postgraduate Educational Management Students' Academic Performance in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The study investigated perceived influence of digital instructional media utilization on postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. Two specific objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. This study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was all 145 postgraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State Universities. The study used the entire population of the students as it was manageable in size. The data collecting instrument for this study is a self-structured questionnaire titled "Perceived Influence of Digital Instructional Media Utilization on Postgraduate Educational Management Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire". The instrument was structured using 4-point rating scale and was face and content validated by the researcher's supervisor and two experts in Measurement and Evaluation in Rivers State University. The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha Statistics and the scores collated yielded an average reliability index of 0.81. All the 145 copies of the questionnaire administered were retrieved and used for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance with a critical value of ± 1.96 . Findings revealed that utilization of Google classroom and digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities to a high extent. Based on the findings, it was recommended among Google classroom should be adopted as a means for instructional delivery including the provision of necessary infrastructural support for it to thrive and government should ensure adequate support for the use of digital textbooks and ensure that all students have equal access to them.

Keywords: *Perceived, Influence, Digital Instructional Media, Educational Management Students, Academic Performance.*

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Introduction

With the arrival of technology, the whole educational system has undergone dramatic changes within the past two decades. These technologies have improved approaches to education especially in teaching. Digital instructional media have emerged as one of the most promising instructional practices in the educational settings. Digital instructional media refers to various types of electronic equipment and materials used to facilitate teaching and learning. According to Caslin (2015) digital instructional media are teaching learning devices that appeal to the auditory and visual senses. Digital instructional media encompasses a wide range of electronic equipment, materials, and technologies used to enhance teaching and learning including audio, visual, and audiovisual tools like computers, projectors, videos, and the internet.

Higgins (2017) opined that digital instructional media brings about positive outcome and enhances retention if properly integrated. It encourages cooperation and collaboration among peers in the same class. It provides courage over one another and offers learners flexible teaching and learning environment. In digital instructional media usage, technology is used to serve multiple learning styles or needs, engage learners, prepare students for life after school, and bring the brick-and-mortar classroom into the 21st century. With the advent of technology and the ease of access it affords, the unique environment for digital instruction can be more easily and successfully created in institutions of learning (Hillinum, 2015).

The effectiveness of digital instructional media has been demonstrated in research literatures. It has been shown to be more effective especially as it affects students' academic performance on average, than other forms of intervention in education. Considering the results of evaluative research in computer assisted learning, university lecturers must be encouraged to utilize the digital instructional media method. Presently, a variety of computer assisted learning software can facilitate not only the delivery of instruction, but also the quality of learning attained by students. For university lecturers to be more competent in the delivery of instruction, their knowledge of various applications of digital instructional media is very pertinent (Heggart & Yoo, 2018). Some of the digital instructional media that are discussed as identified in this study include google classroom and digital textbooks.

Google classroom is an internet-based service provided by Google as an e-learning system (Martinez-Mones, 2017). It is a digital instructional medium and part of the online Google Apps for Education (GAPE), suite of packed productivity applications for teachers and students in learning and online collaboration. This application is downloaded for free, but it must be placed at the level of educational institutions. While GAPE contains many popular Google applications such as Gmail, Google Calendar, and Google Drive, which can be accessed by anyone, Google Classroom is only found at GAPE. This application provides a central site for communicating with students, sending feedback, and providing homework. Some of the main strengths of Google classroom are time-saving and organizational features that are easy to use and very simple. Google classroom is like a virtual extension of brick-and-mortar classrooms. It starts with creating classes and adding students. Then it explores the features found in this application such as sending information, starting discussions, distributing, and collecting tasks (Zhang, 2016).

A digital textbook is an electronic form of a traditional, printed textbook. Teachers and students can use them in any learning environment, whether face-to-face or remote. According to Izenshark and Leahy (2015) students can download a digital textbook or access it online on devices like Chromebooks, iPads, computers, and their phones. Some e-textbooks are simply digitized versions of printed books, while others have interactive features that increase engagement and comprehension. These digital textbooks are sometimes edited by a community or offered on OERs

sites. Educators can also create their own open-source textbooks and share them online (Becta, 2018).

Students' interest and academic performance are dependent on a variety of factors and stand out to reveal how well courses are being taught in institutions of learning. Elenwo and Ebom-Jebose (2023) opined that academic performance is the extent a student has attained his short and long-term educational goals. It is the learning outcomes of the student which includes the knowledge, skills, and ideas acquired and obtained through their course of study within and outside the classroom situation. Presently, digital instructional media can facilitate not only the delivery of instruction, but also the quality of learning attained by students. Hence, Agabi and Okorie (2012) averred that students' cognitive and manipulative performance become more positive after being exposed to digital instructional media. The utilization of these media in teaching and learning is essential, mostly when the expected results have not been achieved in students' performance in examinations. Researchers such as Akbas and Pektus (2021) have shown that most teachers adopt conventional teaching methods which are teacher centered and subsequently result in poor learning outcomes. This brings to limelight the need to investigate perceived influence of digital instructional media utilization on postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Statement of the Problem

Since the internet revolution, there has been a shift in learning due to the development of internet, use of educative online platforms, digital devices, among others. This had led to a dramatic instructional innovative change from traditional to technological pedagogy of teaching in Nigerian universities, and in effect the introduction of various innovative digital technologies. Traditional method of teaching education has had limitation on student learning by focusing on the transfer of knowledge from teacher to students, leading to limited intellectual development, active participation, innovative thinking and a reliance on memorization. Additionally, the shift toward digital instructional media in delivery of lesson has highlighted the need for lecturers to adopt and upgrade in facilities that require value added skills in teaching with the use of zoom, google classroom, WhatApps, digital textbook, open educational resources among others. Furthermore, research has shown that effective leading can only occur when students are made comfortable and important in the classroom, and when their individual learning style are acknowledged and catered to. Overall traditional method of teaching education has limited student engagement, individuality, and the development of critical problem-solving skills as they are primarily passive listeners. These identified problems, therefore, have informed the researcher to conduct a study on perceived influence of digital instructional media utilization on postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the perceived influence of digital instructional media utilization on postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. Specifically, the objectives are to:

1. Examine the extent to which utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.
2. Ascertain the extent to which utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions was answered in this study:

1. To what extent does utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?
2. To what extent does utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Methodology

The research adopted a descriptive survey design. This is because it provides overview of the data that could be used to elicit information from the respondents. The study was conducted in Rivers State. The population of the study was one hundred and forty-five (145) respondents comprising of 62 and 83 Postgraduate Educational Management (EDM) students in the two public Rivers State Universities namely, Rivers State University (RSU) and the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE). The sample size for the study was 145 respondents comprising of 62 Postgraduate EDM Students from Rivers State University and 83 from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, the research instrument for this study was a 10-item researcher's designed questionnaire. The questionnaire was titled "Perceived Influence of Digital Instructional Media Utilization on Postgraduate Educational Management Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (PIEIMUPEMSAPQ)". The instrument was structured using the 4-point summated rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, High Extent (HE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1 point.

The questionnaire was given to an expert in the Department of Educational Management and two other experts in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation to ascertain the face and content validity of the instrument. The Cronbach Alpha Method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. The instrument was administered to 20 postgraduate EDM students selected from the University of Port Harcourt which is outside the universities understudy. The scores collated were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha Statistics and the average reliability coefficient of 0.81 was realized. The researchers administered one hundred and forty-five (145) copies of the questionnaire to the respondents (postgraduate EDM students) with the help of three research assistants. All the copies of the questionnaire were successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion mean score of 2.50 and above was agreed, while the mean score below 2.50 was disagreed. Similarly, the decision rule for the hypotheses was that any

hypotheses with z-calculated value less than the z-critical table value of ± 1.96 was accepted otherwise rejected.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?

Table 1. Mean Perception of Postgraduate Educational Management Students of RSU and IAUE on the Extent Utilization of Google Classroom in Instructional Delivery Influence Student' Academic Performance in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	RSU=62		IAUE=83		RSU & IAUE =145	Remarks
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
1	The use of google classroom allows the creation of classrooms which serves as a means of distributing tasks to students and submission of assignments which enhances their performance.	3.46	0.95	2.96	1.02	3.21	HE
2	The use of google classroom promotes interaction among students for effective performances.	3.27	0.92	2.84	0.98	3.06	HE
3	The use of google classroom gives students the opportunity to provide feedback and get direct input from classmates if they need help when finding difficulty to understand a task that they want to learn more about.	3.10	0.86	2.80	1.04	2.95	HE
4	The use of google classroom helps students to communicate and discuss with their lecturer according to the learning schedule given by the lecturer.	3.25	0.93	3.76	0.93	3.51	HE
5	The use of google classroom provides students with exposure to an online learning system which enhances their academic performance.	3.44	0.78	3.75	1.02	3.60	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	3.30	0.89	3.22	1.00	3.27	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

Table 1 showed the perception of the postgraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State universities on the extent utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence their academic performance in Rivers State universities. Using the criterion mean of 2.50 as the benchmark for acceptance, the data on Table 1 showed that the respondents to a high extent agreed on all the variables with a combined mean of 3.27.

Research Question 2

To what extent does utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities?

Table 2. Mean Perception of Postgraduate Educational Management Students of RSU and IAUE on the Extent Utilization of Digital Textbooks in Instructional Delivery Influence Student' Academic Performance in Rivers State Universities

S/N	Items	RSU=62		IAUE=83		RSU & IAUE =145	Remarks
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
6	The use of digital textbooks enables students to look up for information that supplements or contributes to classroom learning which improves their performance.	2.60	1.06	2.90	1.04	2.75	HE
7	The use of digital textbooks improves students' collaboration and instant messaging to peers about concepts covered in class which enhances their academic performance.	2.99	1.02	2.98	0.98	2.99	HE
8	The use of computer digital textbooks students' engagement in higher levels of processing problems that lead to deeper students learning.	3.25	0.97	2.85	1.06	3.05	HE
9	The use of digital textbooks influences students to explore and generate retentive and self-learning which improves their performance.	3.18	0.94	2.76	0.99	2.97	HE
10	The use of digital textbooks influences students to learn at their own pace for effective performance.	3.54	0.87	2.50	1.02	3.02	HE
	Grand Mean/SD	2.91	0.97	2.80	1.02	2.96	HE

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024.

Table 2 showed the perception of the postgraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State universities on the extent utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence their academic performance in Rivers State universities. Using the criterion mean of 2.50 as the benchmark for acceptance, the data on Table 2 showed that the respondents to a high extent agreed on all the variables with a combined mean of 2.98.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Table 3. z-Test Analysis of the Perception of Postgraduate EDM Students on the Extent of Utilization of Google Classroom in Instructional Delivery on Students' Academic Performance in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
RSU Students	62	3.30	0.89	539	0.05	0.57	±1.96	Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
IAUE Students	83	3.22	1.00					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

Table 3 above shows no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. The z-calculated value of 0.57 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($0.57 < \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 143 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Table 4. z-Test Analysis of the Perception of Postgraduate EDM Students on the Extent of Utilization of Digital Textbooks in Instructional Delivery on Students' Academic Performance in Rivers State Universities

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	DF	LS	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
RSU Students	62	2.91	0.97	143	0.05	0.65	± 1.96	Failed to Reject No Significant Difference
IAUE Students	83	2.80	1.02					

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2024

Table 4 above shows no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. The z-calculated value of 0.65 was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 ($0.65 < \pm 1.96$) for degree of freedom of 143 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted which states that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of postgraduate Educational Management students' of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent to which utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings to research question 1 which looked at the extent utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities showed a grand mean value of 3.30 and 3.22 for RSU and IAUE students respectively. Findings revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, the use of google classroom allows the creation of classrooms which serves as a means of distributing tasks to students and submission of assignments which enhances their performance; promotes interaction among students for effective performances; gives students the opportunity to provide feedback and get direct input from classmates if they need help when finding difficulty to understand a task that they want to learn more about; helps students to communicate and discuss with their lecturer according to the learning schedule given by the lecturer and provides students with exposure to an online learning system which enhances their academic performance. This indicated that both group of respondents; RSU and perceived that utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic

performance. The finding aligns with the findings of Heggart and Yoo (2018) which showed that Google classroom increased student participation and learning and improved classroom dynamics. Result on hypothesis 1 proved that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of students of RSU and IAUE on the extent to which utilization of google classroom in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

The findings to research question 2 which examined the extent utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities showed a grand mean value of 2.91 and 2.80 for RSU and IAUE students respectively. Findings revealed that the respondents agreed to the statements that, the use of digital textbooks enables students to look up for information that supplements or contributes to classroom learning which improves their performance; improves students' collaboration and instant messaging to peers about concepts covered in class which enhances their academic performance; digital textbooks students' engagement in higher levels of processing problems that lead to deeper students learning; influences students to explore and generate retentive and self-learning which improves their performance; influences students to learn at their own pace for effective performance and allows students' control over the rate and sequence of their learning which improves their academic performance. This proved that both group of respondents; RSU and IAUE perceived that utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance The finding is in consonance with the findings of Bersin (2014) which showed that students exposed to the utilization of digital textbooks developed better scientific reasoning skills by engaging in small group discussions and reflections during the classroom work. Result on hypothesis 2 proved that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of students of RSU and IAUE on the extent to which utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities. This indicates that both group of respondents; lecturers of RSU and IAUE perceived fact that utilization of digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that digital instructional media utilization such as google classroom and digital textbooks to a high extent influenced students' academic performance as perceived by postgraduate Educational Management students in Rivers State universities. There is, therefore, no significant difference in the mean perception of RSU and IAUE postgraduate Educational Management students on the extent to which google classroom and digital textbooks in instructional delivery influence postgraduate Educational Management students' academic performance in Rivers State universities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Google classroom should be adopted as a means for instructional delivery including the provision of necessary infrastructural support for it to thrive.
2. Government should ensure adequate support for the use of digital textbooks and ensure that all students have equal access to them.

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